

Sustainable Supply Chain Management and Performance of Logistics Firms in Anambra State - Nigeria

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Abstract

The growing need to create a safe and habitable society has heightened the call for the adoption of sustainable solutions in supply chain management to enhance organizational performance. However, the relationship between sustainable supply chain management practices and the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria, has not been empirically established. Against this background, the researcher conducted an empirical investigation to examine sustainable supply chain management practices and their impact on the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State. The study adopted a survey method. The population comprised 91 registered logistics firms in Anambra State, and the entire population was used as the sample since it was manageable. Data were collected using two structured questionnaire and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and multiple regression were employed for data analysis. The findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices and the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State. Similarly, it was revealed that social sustainable supply chain management practices had a significant positive relationship with the performance of logistics firms. Moreover, it was found that technology and collaboration practices had a significant positive relationship with performance of logistics firms. Furthermore, the findings revealed that sustainable supply chain management practices significantly influence performance of logistics firms. The researcher therefore recommended that logistics firms should improve their environmental and social sustainable supply chain management as well as technology and collaboration practices to enhance firms' performance.

Keywords: Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Performance, Logistics Firms, Environmental, Social, Technology and Collaboration

Introduction

In Nigeria and globally, the logistics industry makes significant contributions to trade and commercial activities. This industry has witnessed substantial growth, driven largely by infrastructure development and the expansion of electronic commerce (e-commerce). However,

Logistics refers to the planning, execution, and coordination of the adequate movement of goods, services, and appropriate communication flows from point of sources of raw materials via product transformation in the factory to point of consumption in order to meet customer requirements and satisfaction (Abul et al., 2019). Managing the flow of products, materials, and resources across the supply chain ensures timely delivery, cost efficiency and customer satisfaction. Islam et al. (2023) stated that logistics involves the management and coordination of the movement of products and goods within the business sector, from the point of production to their final destination. Effective logistics management strengthens business competitiveness in both domestic and global markets, ensuring the reliable and timely delivery of goods and services. Despite facing challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and logistical inefficiencies, the sector remains on a growth trajectory due to increased investments in transportation networks and port modernization (Narula, 2019).

Supply chain management focuses on the coordination of procurement, production, and distribution processes, and incorporates logistics (Onwuchekwa & Nwanyanwu, 2024). Logistics forms a critical component of supply chain management, ensuring the smooth physical movement and storage of goods across the supply chain. Integrating logistics within supply chain management enhances operational efficiency, minimises costs, and improves customer satisfaction. Certainly, effective coordination among supply chain elements plays a crucial role in integrating environmental considerations into sustainable supply chain management. According to Ohue and Akhato (2021), employing supply chain management strategies at higher levels can enhance competitive advantage and optimise organisational performance. Similarly, Baah and Jin (2019) identified a positive correlation between competitive advantage and supply chain management. More recently, Zekhnini, et al. (2021) highlighted the necessity of smarter supply chains to effectively overcome emerging challenges and maintain a competitive edge. Ahi et al. (2016) and Ohue and Akhato (2021) suggested that implementing sustainable supply chain management is essential for improving business performance.

Moreover, sustainability aims to address present demands while safeguarding the capacity of future generations to meet their own needs (Correia, 2019). Sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) refers to the incorporation of environmentally and socially responsible practices across all stages of the supply chain; from raw material procurement to the final delivery of products. This comprehensive strategy ensures that each phase of the supply chain

functions in a manner that preserves ecosystems, upholds human rights, and sustains economic viability. Mbamalu et al. (2023) defined SSCM as the practice of integrating environmental, social, and financial considerations into the sourcing, production, and distribution of goods and services. Green logistics guarantees a more sustainable, cost-effective, and productive supply chain since it leads to the reduction in the production of emissions- vehicles (Nagy & Szentesi, 2024). A comprehensive SSCM approach necessitates that firms modify and restructure their operations to incorporate the management of diverse stakeholder relationships through collaboration and risk-reduction strategies (Ivanov, 2020; Sharma et al., 2022).

More so, sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices (SSCMPs) are essential for ensuring the efficiency and stability of industrial supply chains (Das, 2018). These practices involve the strategic management of materials, capital, human resources, and information through collaboration among supply chain firms, with a focus on maintaining environmental, economic, and social balance for long-term sustainability (Hong et al., 2018). As companies strive to minimise the negative societal and environmental effects of their operations while enhancing financial, market, and operational performance, SSCMPs play a fundamental role in achieving these objectives (Panigrahi et al., 2018). SSCMPs are becoming increasingly essential for logistics firms as they aid in maximising resource efficiency, minimising environmental harm, and enhancing operational effectiveness. Logistics companies are integral to supply chain operations by ensuring the swift movement of goods and services. These firms promote economic, environmental, and social sustainability while improving service efficiency and quality through the integration of sustainable practices into their operations.

Furthermore, logistics firms contribute significantly to economic activities by enhancing supply chain efficiency, reducing transaction costs and improving market accessibility. Despite the sector's importance, there have been concerns regarding the sustainability of logistics operations in the state. Challenges such as inefficient transportation systems, high operational costs, environmental degradation, and regulatory non-compliance have negatively impacted logistics firms' performance. SSCM practices, which involve the integration of environmental, social, and economic considerations into logistics operations have been identified as a potential solution to these challenges. Studies suggest that SSCM enhances efficiency, reduces waste, and improves long-term business viability (Mbamalu et al., 2023). However, the adoption of sustainable

logistics practices remains limited, with many firms continuing to rely on conventional and unsustainable methods. Unfortunately, poor infrastructure, financial constraints and a lack of awareness about the benefits of sustainability further hinder the implementation of SSCM in the logistics sector. Ekakitie-Emonena et al. (2024) noted that empirical research has demonstrated that sustainable practices in supply chain management can enhance operational performance and competitiveness. Hence, logistics firms that implement eco-friendly transportation, energy-efficient warehousing, and waste reduction strategies are more likely to achieve cost savings and regulatory compliance while improving their corporate reputation. Despite these potential benefits, there is a paucity of studies examining the direct relationship between SSCM practices and the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State. This study seeks to bridge this research gap by investigating the impact of sustainable supply chain management practices on the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Sustainable Supply Chain Management

Supply chain management (SCM) involves a range of managerial activities that involve sourcing raw materials, manufacturing and assembling products, overseeing warehousing and inventory, monitoring supply and demand and ensuring the distribution, and delivery of finished goods to customers. SSCM entails embedding environmental, social, and economic considerations into the planning, design, operation, and regulation of supply chain activities. This approach seeks to mitigate adverse environmental and social impacts while enhancing sustainability outcomes. According to Hong et al. (2018), SSCM practices include both the internal and external organisational strategies aimed at ensuring sustainability across all three dimensions of sustainability—environmental, social, and economic. Gold and Schleper (2017) opined that the key aspects of SSCM involve inventory control, eco-friendly product design, supervision of production processes, product modifications, and efficient management of energy consumption, waste disposal, logistics, and emission reduction. Similarly, Raut et al. (2017) defined SSCM as a management approach that integrates environmental, social, and economic factors into business operations. Incidentally, the fluctuation of consumer demands and the complexity of product components have intensified both internal competition among businesses and external competition in the global market.

Additionally, SSCM represents a nonlinear progression from traditional SCM to a more comprehensive approach that integrates social and environmental considerations. It essentially merges avant-garde SCM practices with sustainability principles (Barata et al., 2024). This approach systematically incorporates the three core dimensions of sustainability like environmental, social, and economic in a synergistic manner, thus promoting enhanced transparency in supply chain operations. Subsequently, Mbamalu et al. (2023) defined SSCM as a strategic, transparent integration and achievement of an organisation's social, environmental, and economic goals in the systemic coordination of key inter-organisational business processes for improving the long-term economic performance of the individual company and its supply chains. Also, Seuring and Müller (2008) asserted that SSCM entails the management of material, information and capital flows while fostering collaboration among businesses across the supply chain with a strong emphasis on all three pillars of sustainable development. This approach ensures that supply chain processes align with sustainability objectives which could lead to improved operational efficiency and long-term value creation.

Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices

Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices(SSCMP)integrate environmental, social, and technological considerations into supply chain operations (Baah & Jin, 2019). This integration aims to enhance sustainability, operational efficiency, and stakeholder engagement. Scholars and practitioners have extensively explored these dimensions, providing valuable insights into effective SSCM practices.

Environmentally Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices

Environmental sustainability within supply chains focuses on minimizing ecological footprints through strategic resource management and waste reduction. Coyle et al. (2016) emphasized the importance of adopting green logistics practices such as optimizing transportation routes and utilizing energy-efficient warehousing to reduce carbon emissions and operational costs. These practices not only mitigate environmental impact but also enhance economic performance. Also, the adoption of closed-loop supply chains as discussed by Ahmed et al. (2020), involves designing supply networks that facilitate product returns, recycling, and remanufacturing. This approach promotes resource efficiency and aligns with environmental sustainability goals by

reducing waste and conserving materials. With these contributions, the researchers hypothesise that:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices and performance of logistics firms in Anambra State.

Social Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices

Social sustainability in supply chains addresses the ethical and societal impacts of business operations. Mbamalu et al. (2023) defined SSCM as the strategic integration of an organization's social, environmental, and economic objectives to enhance long-term economic performance. Nwaulune et al. (2023) remarked that social sustainability encompasses various aspects, including fair labor practices, employee welfare, community engagement, and ethical sourcing. Boyer et al. (2016) identified five distinct perspectives on the social pillar of sustainability. According to their classification, social sustainability is regarded as an independent goal or the third pillar of sustainability, a limiting factor on economic and environmental priorities, a prerequisite for thriving economic and environmental systems, often termed social capital, a catalyst for environmental and economic transformation, and an integrated, locally grounded and process-driven approach to sustainability. The fifth perspective is considered the most effective, as it provides a comprehensive and systemic understanding of sustainability while incorporating local knowledge and experiences. This involves ensuring fair labor practices, promoting diversity, and engaging in community development initiatives. Ekakitie-Emonena (2024) noted that social sustainability practices positively influence supply chain performance. By fostering ethical labor practices and community engagement, companies can enhance their reputation, customer loyalty, and operational resilience. Upon these contributions, the researchers propose that:

H2: There is a significant positive relationship between social sustainable supply chain management practices and performance of logistics firms in Anambra State.

Technology and Collaboration Practices in Sustainable Supply Chain Management

Technological innovation and collaboration are important for advancing SSCM. Chen et al. (2017) opined that supply chain collaboration, supported by advanced technologies leads to improved sustainability outcomes. The integration of digital tools such as blockchain and data analytics, enhances supply chain transparency, traceability, and efficiency. Moreover, leveraging technology-driven supplier collaboration is essential for building resilient and sustainable supply

chains. Anzola (2023) asserted that collaboration enables manufacturers to meet environmental, social, and governance (ESG) expectations while enhancing operational performance. This collaborative approach fosters shared sustainability goals and joint investments in green technologies. With these inputs the researchers tentatively state that:

H3: There is a significant positive relationship between technology and collaboration practices and performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Business Performance

High business performance is essential for competitive advantage, organizational success, and survival (Attamah et al., 2023). Business performance is a widely applied concept across various fields. It refers to the extent to which a mechanism or process achieves its intended objectives. In the realm of enterprise management, business performance encompasses the efficiency and effectiveness with which an organisation meets its strategic goals, financial targets, and operational benchmarks. It is a multidimensional construct that incorporates financial performance, operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, innovation, and sustainability (Neely et al., 2002). For instance, financial performance which is often measured through indicators such as revenue growth, profitability, and return on investment (ROI), remains a primary focus for organisations seeking economic viability. Kaplan and Norton (1992) extended performance measurement beyond financial metrics to include customer perspectives, internal processes and learning, and growth dimensions. This comprehensive approach ensures that businesses evaluate performance comprehensively, rather than relying solely on financial indicators. Ewuzie et al. (2019) noted that logistics performance depends on the information sharing capability in which firms leverage on to achieve high success. Okolo et al. (2023) observe that firms will perform and compete poorly if they fail to incorporate sustainable practices in their operation capability.

Operational efficiency is another critical component of business performance, encompassing aspects such as productivity, cost management, and supply chain optimisation. According to Porter (1985), organisations that continuously improve their operational processes gain competitive advantages, leading to enhanced performance outcomes. Firms investing in lean management and process automation often achieve higher levels of efficiency and adaptability to market changes. Customer satisfaction and brand reputation are also integral to business performance, as they directly influence customer loyalty and market share. Sustainability has

emerged as a key determinant of business performance in the modern corporate business environment. Elkington (1997) introduced the triple bottom line (TBL) framework, which evaluates performance based on the economic, social, and environmental dimensions. Organisations that integrate sustainable practices such as corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives and green supply chain management not only enhance their reputation but also mitigate risks associated with regulatory compliance and stakeholder expectations.

Review of Empirical Studies

Ekakitie-Emonena (2024) investigated the impact of sustainable supply chain management practices on the competitive advantage of brewery companies in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study employed a cross-sectional survey research design, selecting a sample of 152 employees from a total population of 250. A stratified random sampling technique was utilised and data collection was conducted through a structured questionnaire. The instrument's validity was ensured through content validation, while reliability was assessed using a test-retest method. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were employed to examine the relationship between sustainable supply chain management practices and competitive advantage. The findings indicated a significant and positive correlation between supply chain collaboration ($r = 0.537$, $p < 0.01$), corporate social responsibility ($r = 0.325$, $p < 0.01$), supply chain transparency ($r = 0.573$, $p < 0.01$) and reverse logistics ($r = 0.554$, $p < 0.01$) with competitive advantage. The study concluded that sustainable supply chain management practices play a crucial role in enhancing the competitive advantage of brewery companies in Anambra State.

Mbamalu et al. (2023) conducted a study to explore the relationship between sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) and organisational performance (OP) from the perspectives of academics and practitioners in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design and data were collected from 122 respondents through structured questionnaires. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analyses to test the formulated hypotheses. The findings revealed that the dynamic capabilities (DC) components of collaboration and resilience had a positive relationship with organisational performance, although resilience was not statistically significant.

Iherobiem (2023) conducted a study to examine the effect of sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) practices on the innovative performance of manufacturing firms in

Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, targeting three Nigerian manufacturing firms. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 120 respondents and data collection was conducted using structured questionnaires. A pilot study was carried out to assess the validity and reliability of the research instrument, achieving a 91% response rate. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, with results presented in tables and percentages. The findings indicated that SSCM practices had a positive and significant impact on the innovative performance of manufacturing firms. Specifically, the study found that the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability all contributed significantly to innovation performance.

Egunlae (2024) conducted a study to examine the role of sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) as a strategic tool for enhancing organisational performance and competitiveness among manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study aimed to identify the necessary guidelines and practices required for achieving sustainability in supply chain management and to explore the relationship between SSCM practices and business profitability. The study adopted a descriptive research design, utilising structured questionnaires to collect data from manufacturing firms. The findings, presented in tables, revealed that awareness of sustainable practices was slightly above average, with varying degrees of adoption across different SSCM practices. Specifically, 37% of firms implemented reverse logistics, 75% adopted sustainable warehousing, 26% engaged in environmental purchasing and only 4% incorporated sustainable transportation.

Nwaulune et al. (2023) conducted an empirical investigation into the impact of green logistics practices on the social sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) firms in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study was motivated by the increasing emphasis on social sustainability in organisational operations and the observed challenges FMCG firms face in integrating environmentally friendly logistics practices into their supply chain management systems. The study employed a survey research design, targeting a population of 13,782 management staff from eight listed FMCG firms in Lagos State. Using the Taro Yamane formula, a sample size of 519 respondents was determined and data were collected through a structured and validated questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.78 to 0.94 and a high response rate of 96.7% was recorded. The data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, including multiple and hierarchical

regression analyses. The findings revealed that green logistics practices—such as green production, green procurement, green transportation, green packaging and reverse logistics—had a statistically significant effect on the social sustainability of the selected FMCG firms (Adj. $R^2 = 0.066$, $F(5, 496) = 8.036$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that adopting green logistics practices contributes positively to the social sustainability performance of FMCG firms in Lagos State. It recommended that management adopt a holistic approach by incorporating green logistics into broader sustainability strategies to enhance long-term social sustainability.

Opara and Owuso (2021) examined the impact of sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) practices on petroleum marketing firms within Nigeria's oil and gas industry. The researchers employed a cross-sectional survey design, focusing on a population of 450 independent petroleum marketers in Rivers State. Using the Yamane (1967) formula, a sample size of 212 respondents—including directors, station managers, station supervisors and depot representatives—was selected for the study. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient with the aid of SPSS version 22. The findings indicated a strong, positive and significant relationship between SSCM practices and corporate social responsibility (CSR) within petroleum marketing firms. The study concluded that petroleum firms that adopt SSCM practices tend to enhance their CSR performance, leading to improved stakeholder relations and competitive advantage.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational survey design. The research was conducted in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 91 registered firms offering logistic services in Anambra State. The entire population was sampled for the study because it was manageable. Two discrete copies of structured questionnaire were used to collect data for the study. The first question collected information on sustainable supply chain management practices (environmentally sustainable supply chain management, social sustainable supply chain management and technology and collaboration practices). The second questionnaire collected information of indicators of business performance. The questions were modified from prior research to ensure reliability and validity. The instrument was structured on a 5-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD). Validity of the instrument was ensured through a two-step approach: initially, the questionnaire was pretested in

a pilot study and subsequently, it was modified with the assistance of three marketing experts at the Department of Marketing, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach's alpha tests were conducted to determine reliability. As demonstrated in Table 1, the results indicated that all variables surpassed the threshold alpha value of 0.70, confirming their reliability. The instrument was distributed by the researcher with the assistance of two research assistants. The research assistants were trained on the mode of instrument administration and retrieval. Out of 91 copies of questionnaire administered on the respondents, 84 copies were returned in good condition and used for data analysis. Pearson product moment correlation was used to answer the research questions. The hypothesis was tested using multiple regression analysis. The co-efficient “r” obtained was used to ascertain how each of the independent variables correlate the dependent variable. In interpreting the values of the null hypotheses, when p-value is less than or equal to .05 ($p \leq .05$), the null hypothesis was rejected. On the other hand, when the p-value is greater than .05 ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices (ESSCMP) and performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis between Environment Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices and Performance of Logistics Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria

		Environment Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices	Performance of Logistics Firms	Remark
Environment Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices	Pearson Correlation	1	.752**	High Positive relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	84	84	
Performance of Logistics Firms	Pearson Correlation	.752**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	84	84	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Study, 2025

Data in Table 2 reveals that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is $r=0.75$. This shows that environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices have a high positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. This implies that the adoption of environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices would improve the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Thus, environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices have a high positive relationship with the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between social sustainable supply chain management practices (SSSCMP) and performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis between Social Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices and Performance of Logistics Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria

		Social Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices	Performance of Logistics Firms	Remark
Social Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices	Pearson Correlation	1	.770**	High Positive relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	84	84	
Performance of Logistics Firms	Pearson Correlation	.770**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	84	84	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Study, 2025

Data in Table 3 reveals that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is $r=0.77$. This shows that social sustainable supply chain management practices have a high

positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. This implies that the adoption of social sustainable supply chain management practices would improve the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Thus, social sustainable supply chain management practices have a high positive relationship with the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship between technology and collaboration practices (TCP) and performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Summary of Pearson Correlation Analysis between Technology and Collaboration Practices and Performance of Logistics Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria

		Technology and Collaboration Practices	Performance of Logistics Firms	Remark
Technology and Collaboration Practices	Pearson Correlation	1	.812**	High Positive relationship
	Sig, (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	84	84	
Performance of Logistics Firms	Pearson Correlation	.812**	1	
	Sig, (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	84	84	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Study, 2025

Data in Table 4 reveals that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is $r=0.81$. This shows that technology and collaboration practices have a high positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. This implies that the adoption of technology and collaboration practices would improve the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Thus, technology and collaboration practices have a high positive relationship with the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State.

Null Hypothesis

Sustainable supply chain management practices do not have any significant relationship with the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Test of significance of Multiple Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Sustainable Supply Chain Management Practices and Performance of Logistics Firms

	Unstandar dized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	53.005	5.765		48.550	.000
ESSCMP	.322	.110	.516	8.065	.000
SSSCMP	.388	.121	.332	5.047	.000
TCP	.443	.274	.600	14.003	.000
R	.747				
R ²	.628				
Adj. R ²	.709				
F	58.455				.000

The summary of the test of significance of regression analysis as shown in Table 5 show that the regression coefficient (R) is .747 while the R² is .628 and Adjust R² is .709. The F-ratio associated with regression is 58.455 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance .05, the study therefore did not accept the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship between sustainable supply chain management practices and the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices have a significant positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The finding of the study indicates that environmental SSCM practices such as green logistics, reverse logistics, and energy-efficient transportation contribute significantly to reducing operational costs while improving resource efficiency. Logistics firms that adopt these practices would experience lower fuel consumption, reduced waste generation, and improved supply chain transparency which can improve business performance. This is in agreement with Ekakitie-Emonena (2024) who found that sustainable supply chain practices like supply chain

transparency and reverse logistics had a significant positive correlation with the competitive advantage of companies. Similarly, Egunlae (2024) reported that while awareness of sustainable supply chain practices was moderate, firms that adopted sustainable warehousing (75%) and reverse logistics (37%) experienced notable improvements in business profitability. On the other hand, adopting environmentally SSCM practices enables logistics firms to align with global sustainability standards which can enhance their reputation and market positioning. Companies that integrate green logistics and sustainable procurement into their supply chain operations often gain a competitive edge by attracting environmentally conscious customers and investors. This is supported by Iherobiem (2023) who found that SSCM practices significantly influenced the innovative performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Iherobiem stated that firms implementing sustainable supply chain practices, particularly in the economic, environmental, and social dimensions, reported increased innovation and competitiveness.

Similarly, the finding of the study revealed that social sustainable supply chain management practices have a significant positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. One possible reason for the positive relationship between SSSCM practices and firm performance is the role of supply chain collaboration and corporate social responsibility in fostering business sustainability. Firms that integrate social sustainability into their supply chain management tend to build strong stakeholder relationships, improve customer trust, and enhance brand reputation. The study by Ekakitie-Emonena (2024) supports this finding, as it found a significant and positive correlation between supply chain collaboration and corporate social responsibility with competitive advantage in brewery companies in Anambra State. This suggests that firms that prioritise social sustainability through collaboration with suppliers and ethical labour practices can achieve greater competitive positioning and consequently improve organisational performance. Also, another reason for the positive relationship observed in this study is the ability of SSSCM practices to enhance organisational resilience and innovation. Hence, through the adoption of ethical sourcing, fair labour practices, and community engagement, logistics firms can create a work environment that fosters innovation and long-term sustainability. This is in consonance with Iherobiem (2023) who reported that SSCM practices significantly enhance the innovative performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study found that the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability all contributed to innovation, which, in turn impacted positively on firm performance. This agrees with the

findings of the present study, reinforcing the argument that social sustainability practices are critical for business growth and long-term viability. These findings contribute to the growing body of literature affirming that sustainable supply chain management is not only an ethical imperative but also a strategic competitive advantage for firms seeking improved performance and competitive sustainability.

Furthermore, the finding of the study revealed that technology and collaboration practices have a high positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The integration of technology in sustainable supply chain management facilitates real-time tracking, automation, and data-driven decision-making, leading to improved logistics operations. Technology-driven solutions such as cloud computing, blockchain, and artificial intelligence enhance supply chain transparency, reduce delays, and optimise resource utilisation. This efficiency ultimately contributes to improved organisational performance. The findings of Ekakitie-Emonena (2024), is in agreement with this finding since the study demonstrated that supply chain transparency had a significant positive correlation with the competitive advantage of brewery companies in Anambra State. The study underscored the role of transparency, which is often driven by technological advancements in enhancing sustainable supply chain practices. Similarly, Iherobiem (2023) found that sustainable supply chain management practices significantly influenced the innovative performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, highlighting that economic, environmental, and social sustainability dimensions contributed to improved innovation. This finding reinforces the argument that technology plays a crucial role in enhancing logistics firms' performance through sustainable practices.

More so, effective collaboration among supply chain stakeholders fosters resource sharing, risk mitigation, and process integration, leading to enhanced organisational performance. Collaboration enables logistics firms to strengthen supplier relationships, streamline distribution networks, and improve responsiveness to market demands. This is supported by the findings of Mbamalu et al. (2023) who found that collaboration and resilience in dynamic capabilities positively influenced organisational performance. Although resilience was not statistically significant, collaboration emerged as a key determinant of performance, reinforcing the importance of cooperative strategies in sustainable supply chain management. Additionally, Ekakitie-Emonena (2024) reported a significant correlation between supply chain collaboration

and competitive advantage, further validating the present study's findings that collaboration strengthens business performance.

Conclusion

The researchers conclude that sustainable supply chain management practices have significant positive relationship with performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. This means that the application of sustainable supply chain management practices would improve the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The application of environmentally sustainable supply chain management practices, social sustainable supply chain management practices, and technology and collaboration practices would improve the performance of logistics firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. It is therefore imperative that environmentally conscious logistics firm should put in place measures to facilitate the smooth application of sustainable supply chain management practices. It is against these findings that the researchers recommend that logistics firms should prioritise environmentally sustainable supply chain management by adopting eco-friendly transportation, energy-efficient warehousing, and waste reduction strategies. These firms should also invest in carbon footprint reduction initiatives to comply with environmental regulations and enhance corporate sustainability. Similarly, logistics Firms should integrate fair labour practices, employee welfare programmes, and community engagement initiatives into their supply chain operations. This can be done by promoting ethical sourcing and corporate social responsibility activities to promote stakeholder trust for long-term business success.

In addition, logistics firm investment in modern supply chain technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and real-time tracking systems should be encouraged. These technologies will enhance transparency, improve data management, and facilitate efficient decision-making within logistics operations. They should also establish strong partnerships with suppliers, distributors, and customers to improve resource sharing and supply chain resilience. Subsequently, engaging in strategic alliances and joint ventures will enhance operational efficiency and foster innovation within the industry. And finally, they should organise continuous training programmes to equip employees with the necessary skills to implement sustainable supply chain management practices. Also, workshops and professional certifications should be encouraged to enhance workforce competency in sustainable supply chain management.

References

- Abdul, F. A., Iortimbir, A. I., Oladipo, G. T., & Olota, O. O. (2019). Impact of logistics management on organizational performance (A case study of Dangote Flour Mills Plc, Nigeria). *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 21(1), 136-49.
- Ahmed, Z. Z., M.W. Ali, S. & Danish, A. (2020). Linking urbanization, human capital, and the ecological footprint in G7 Countries: An empirical analysis. *Sustainable Cities & Societies*, 55, 102064.
- Ahi, P. Mohamad Y. & Jaber, S. C. (2016). A comprehensive multidimensional framework for assessing the performance of sustainable supply chains. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 40, 23-24.
- Anzola, V. (2022). *Technology-enabled supplier collaboration holds the key to more sustainable supply chains*. <https://o9solutions.com/articles/technology-enabled-supplier-collaboration-sustainable-supply-chains/>.
- Attamah, I., Okolo, V. O., Okoro, D., Ikpo, K., & Nnadi, N. (2023). The effect of recruitment and selection on salesperson performance of a vehicle manufacturing company in Nigeria. *Innovative Marketing*, 19(2), 115-128.
- Baah, C. & Jin, Z. (2019). Sustainable supply chain management and organizational performance: The intermediary role of competitive advantage. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 9, 119–131.
- Barata, F., Ricardianto, P., Haq, L., Octaviani, R., Ariohadi, M., Sitorus, P., & Endri, E. (2024). Safety risk and operational efficiency on logistic service providers' sustainable coal supply chain management. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 12(1), 461-470.
- Boyer, R. H. W., Peterson, N. D., Arora, P., & Caldwell, K. (2016). Five approaches to social sustainability and an integrated way forward. *Sustainability*, 8, 878. 1-18.
- Chen, J., Sohal, A. S., & Prajogo, D. I. (2017). Supply chain collaboration for sustainability: A literature review and future research agenda. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 20(4), 360-384.
- Correia M. S. (2019). Sustainability: An Overview of the Triple Bottom Line and Sustainability Implementation. *International Journal of Strategic Engineering*, 2(1), 29-38.
- Coyle, J. J., Thomchick, E. A., & Ruamsook, K. (2016). Environmentally sustainable supply chain management: An evolutionary framework. *Supply Chain Management Review*, 20(5), 10-17.
- Das, D. (2018). The impact of Sustainable Supply Chain Management practices on firm performance: Lessons from Indian organizations. *Journal of Clean Production*, 203, 179–196. DOI:10.9734/BJEMT/2016/1992.
- Egunlae, O. O. (2024). Sustainable supply chain management: The right way of doing business in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 12(2), 2551–2570.
- Ekakitie-Emonena, S., Onyenanu, C. O., & Otutuadum, D. (2024). Sustainable supply chain management practices and competitive advantage of brewery firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Accounting, Finance & Management Research (IJAAFMR)*, 8(4), 78-89.
- Elkington, J. (1997). *Cannibals with forks: The triple bottom line of 21st-century business*. Capstone.

- Ewuzie, C., Ugwuonah, G., Okolo, V. O., Okocha, E., & Agu, A. O. (2023). Stimulators of third-party logistics performance of supply chains in the Nigerian manufacturing industry. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(3), 176-188.
- Gold, S. & Schleper, M.C. (2017). A pathway towards true sustainability: A recognition foundation of sustainable supply chain management. *European Management Journal*. 35, 425–429.
- Hong, J., Zhang, Y., & Ding, M. (2018). Sustainable supply chain management practices, supply chain dynamic capabilities, and enterprise performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 3508–3519.
- Iherobiem A.C. (2023). The effect of sustainable supply chain management on firm innovative performance: A study of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Logistics, Purchasing and Supply Chain Management*, 11 (3), 1-14.
- Islam, Md. R., Monjur, Md. E. I., & Akon, T. (2023). Supply chain management and logistics: how important interconnection is for business success. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 11, 2505-2524.
- Ivanov, D. (2020). Predicting the impacts of epidemic outbreaks on global supply chains: A simulation-based analysis on the coronavirus outbreak (COVID-19/SARS-CoV-2) case. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 136, 1-14.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1992). The balanced scorecard: Measures that drive performance. *Harvard Business Review*, 70(1), 71-79.
- Mbamalu, E. I., Chike, N. K., Oguanobi, C. A., & Egbunike, C. F. (2023). Sustainable supply chain management and organizational performance: Perception of academics and practitioners. *Annals of Management and Organization Research*, 5(1), 13-30.
- Nagy, G., & Szentesi, S. (2024). Green logistics: Transforming supply chains for a sustainable future. *Advanced Logistic Systems – Theory and Practice*, 18(3), 29-42.
- Narula, A. (2019). *Nigeria logistics and warehousing market outlook to 2023*. Ken Research. <https://www.kenresearch.com/industry-reports/nigeria-logistics-and-warehousing-market>.
- Neely, A., Gregory, M., & Platts, K. (2002). Performance measurement system design: A literature review and research agenda. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 25(12), 1228-1263.
- Nwaulune, J. C., Ajike, E. O., & Bamidele, A. G. (2023). The impact of green logistics practices on social sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods firms in Lagos State, Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *International Research Journal of Economics and Management Studies*, 2(2), 432-444.
- Ohue, P. I., & Akhator, P. A. (2021). Supply chain management and performance of brewing firms in South-South, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Business and Economic Management*, 4(1), 13-18.
- Okolo, V. O., Ohanagorom, M. I., Okocha, E. R., Muoneke, O. B., & Okere, K. I. (2023). Does financing SMEs guarantee inclusive growth and environmental sustainability in the European union? *Heliyon*, 9, 1-26.

- Onwuchekwa, D., & Nwanyanwu, M. O. (2024). Global supply chain management and the performance of multi-national companies in Rivers State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 12(7), 64-79.
- Opara, B. C., & Owuso, S. M. (2021). Sustainable supply chain management practices and corporate social responsibility of petroleum marketing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Marketing Systems*, 13(9), 44-55.
- Panigrahi, S.S., Bahinipati, B. & Jain, V. (2019). Sustainable supply chain management: A review of literature and implications for future research. *Management of Environmental Quality*, 30 (5), 1001-1049.
- Porter, M. E. (1985). *Competitive advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance*. Free Press.
- Raut, R. D., Narkhede, B., & Gardas, B. B. (2017). To identify the critical success factors of sustainable supply chain management practices in the context of oil and gas industries: ISM approach. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 68, 33-47.
- Seuring, S., & Müller, M. (2008). From a literature review to a conceptual framework for sustainable supply chain management. *Journal of cleaner production*, 16(15), 1699-1710.
- Sharma, M., & Joshi, S. (2019). Brand sustainability among young consumers: an AHP-TOPSIS approach. *Young Consumers*, 20(4), 314-337.
- Zekhnini, K. Cherrafi, A. Bouhaddou, I. Benghabrit, Y. & Garza-Reyes, J.A. (2021). Supply chain management 4.0: A literature review and research framework. *Benchmarking International Journal* 28, 465–501.